

Work-Family Conflict Disaster: From Organizational Commitment to Job Satisfaction

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This study aimed to measure the effect of work-family conflict on job satisfaction through organizational commitment (affective, continuance, normative) as mediation. The data collection was done by simple random sampling to 251 population of woman employee in an automotive industry in Tangerang. The returned and valid questionnaire results were 170 samples. Data processing was used in SEM method with Smarts 3.0 software. The results of this study concluded that work-family conflicts have not significant effect on job satisfaction, work-family conflict have significant effect on organizational commitment (affective, continuance, normative), and organizational commitment (continuance and normative) have mediating effect on relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction, except affective commitment have not significant effect on job satisfaction. This new research proposed a model for building job satisfaction among women employee of automotive industry in Tangerang through enhancing organizational commitment and by manage the work-family conflict. This research could pave the way to improve woman employee readiness in facing the era of industrial revolution 4.0.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work-family conflict.*

INTRODUCTION

A common and growing belief in our society is that professional life at work and family are two independent and separate life domain. Whereas in fact, these two worlds are not totally separate, but instead influence each other and are not independent (Sabari, 2015; Asbari, Chi Hyun, et al., 2020; Asbari, Purwanto, Faysal, et al., 2020; Asbari, Purwanto, Maisarah, et al., 2020; Goestjahjanti et al., 2020; Maisarah et al. ., 2020; Ramono et al., 2020; Sopa et al., 2020). Several studies have concluded that the relationship between work and family is highly interdependent and dynamic (Huang et al., 2004). Factors in the world of work influence family life and vice versa (Boyar & Mosley Jr, 2007). Studies also identify various antecedents and mediating factors between work and family roles (Asbari, Bernardo, et al., 2020; Asbari, Ramono, et al., 2020; Supardi et al., 2020). Work-family conflict (WFC) occurs when one role (for example, as a parent) interferes with involvement in another role (for example, as an employee) (Greenhaus & Beutel, 1985). Research on the WFC usually analyzes the interaction conflict between these two dual roles. Several research on the WFC has investigated a variety of factors, such as marital status, child care responsibilities, and job stress (Boyar & Mosley Jr, 2007). However, however, the emergence of the WFC really depends on interactions with superiors and other people in the immediate environment, both at work and at home (Grandey et al., 2005). Furthermore, researchers (Luk & Shaffer, 2005; Poelmans et al., 2003) pointing out that the shortage of existing research is that most of it is conducted in the US and other western countries; Little research has

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been done in Indonesia, especially in the automotive industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Work-Family Conflict

According to (Greenhaus & Beutel, 1985) Work-family conflict is a form of inter-role conflict, namely the pressure or imbalance of roles between roles at work and roles in the family. High working hours and heavy workloads are a direct sign of a work-family conflict due to the excessive time and effort spent working. This results in a lack of time and energy that can be used for family activities. (Greenhaus & Beutel, 1985) Describe the types of conflict associated with the dilemma of women's roles between household and work. First, time-based conflict, is a conflict that occurs because time is used to fulfill one role and cannot be used to fulfill other roles, including the division of time, energy and opportunities between work and household roles. In this case, scheduling is difficult and time-limited when the demands and behaviors required to play the two don't match. Second, strain-based conflict, which refers to the emergence of tension or emotional state that is generated by one role, makes it difficult for a person to fulfill the demands of another role. For example, a mother who works all day will feel tired, and it makes it difficult to sit comfortably with the child completing his homework. This role tension can include stress, increased blood pressure, anxiety, emotional states, and headaches. Third, behavior-based conflict is a conflict that arises when expectations from behavior are different from expectations from other role behaviors. The mismatch of individual behavior at work and at home, which is due to differences in the rules of behavior of a career woman, is usually difficult to swap between the roles she plays with one another. is a conflict that arises when the expectations of behavior are different from the expectations of other role behaviors. The mismatch of individual behavior at work and at home, which is due to differences in the rules of behavior of a career woman, is usually difficult to swap between the roles she plays with one another. is a conflict that arises when the expectations of behavior are different from the expectations of other role behaviors. The mismatch of individual behavior at work and at home, which is due to differences in the rules of behavior of a career woman, is usually difficult to swap between the roles she plays with one another.

Organizational Commitment

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is defined as a an individual's emotional attachment to the organization is characterized by an acceptance of organizational values and a willingness to remain with the organization (Somers, 1995). Individuals with strong affective commitment will tend to behave in the best interests of the organization (John P. Meyer et al., 1997). Research has identified several antecedents for affective commitment, including leadership (Ribeiro et al., 2018), personality, self-efficacy and job resources (Albrecht et al., 2017). Employees tend to have stronger affective bonds when their experiences in an organization are consistent with their expectations (JP Meyer & Allen, 1997). As noted above, when individual values and self-fulfillment are felt to be in accordance with what employees receive from the company, they are more likely to have a high commitment to their organization (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990; Perre we et al., 1999). Adopting a social identity theory framework, research (Harris &

Cameron, 2005) found that affective commitment was able to predict psychological well-being employees. Likewise research (Clarke & Mahadi, 2017; Negi I ik, 2020; Saha & Kumar, 2018). Therefore, the authors need to formulate a hypothesis about the relationship between affective commitment and job satisfaction. Likewise, how is the relationship between work-family conflict and affective commitment (Tumiran et al., 2020; Nuriyati et al., 2020; Purwanto; et al., 2019; Sutiono et al., 2020; Juwono, Novita sari, Huta Galung, et al., 2020).

Continuance Commitment

Continuance commitment is a commitment that arises when employees remain in an organization because of the need for salaries and other benefits, or because employees do not find other work alternatives. (John P Meyer et al., 1993). Research (Khan et al., 2016) mentioned that there is a significant correlation between continuance commitment and job satisfaction. However, other studies concluded that no statistical significance was found between happiness at work and continuance commitment (Pepey et al., 2016). Thus, the authors hypothesize on the relationship between continuance commitment and job satisfaction. Likewise, the WFC relationship and continuance commitment.

Normative Commitment

Normative commitment is a commitment that arises from values in employees. An employee stays in an organization because he has the awareness that commitment to the organization is what he should do (John P Meyer et al., 1993).

Individual work ethics or values closely related to his attitude towards work. Desire for upward career mobility, attitude toward appreciation, and levels of job involvement are all linked to individual work ethic (Yousef, 2001). Eastern and western cultures differ substantially (Ralston et al., 2008). The main difference between East and West work ethics has actually been influenced by religious beliefs. While Western culture emphasizes duty and personal responsibility towards oneself, while Eastern culture emphasizes commitment to family and groups (Ralston et al., 2008). Still according (Yousef, 2001), it can be said that individuals who are strongly supports a positive work ethic tends to be more committed to the organization. In addition, the individual feels compelled to reciprocate with commitment because of receiving a reward from organization. Based on these studies and analysis, the authors hypothesize the relationship between normative commitment and job satisfaction. Also analyze the relationship between WFC and normative commitment (Asbari et al., 2019; Cahyono et al., 2020; Chider et al., 2020; Imelda et al., 2020; Kusumaningsih et al., 2020; Novita sari et al., 2020; Sili Tonga et al., 2020; Juwono, Novita sari, Sabari, et al., 2020).

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a pleasant or positive emotional state that results from a person's assessment of his work or experience (Armstrong et al., 2015; Balyo's et al., 2019; Chordia et al., 2017; Eliyana et al., 2019; Hedayat et al., 2018; It, 2011; Qureshi et al., 2019; Sabahi & Sanai Dashti, 2016). In other words, job satisfaction; in this case, a teacher's job satisfaction is a positive or negative emotion as a result of the teacher's evaluation of the level of satisfaction with his job. Therefore, job satisfaction is one of the most frequently measured organizational variables in research and has been widely

studied in organizational behavior. Job satisfaction has been shown to be an important indicator of how workers feel about their jobs and predictors of work behavior such as motivation, absenteeism and performance. (Bogler, 2001; Onyema et al., 2018).

Operational Definition of Variables and Indicators

Method used in this research is quantitative method. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to all married female employees in one of the automotive industries in Tangerang. The instrument used to measure work-family conflict was adapted from (Grandey et al., 2005) using 11 items (WFC1-WFC11). Organizational commitment, which includes the affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment, which are adapted from (Allen & Meyer, 1990) using 6 items for affective commitment (AC1-AC6), 4 items for continuance commitment (CC1-CC4), and 4 items for normative commitment (NC1-NC4). Job satisfaction adapted from (Armstrong et al., 2015) by using 5 items (JS1-JS5). The list of variables and items is mentioned in Table 1. The questionnaire is designed closed except for questions / statements regarding the identity of the respondent in the form of a semi-open questionnaire. Each closed question / statement item is given five answer options, namely: strongly agree score 5, agree score 4, neutral / doubt score 3, disagree score 2, and strongly disagree score 1. The method for processing data is by using PLS and using SmartPLS version 3.0 software as a tool.

Population and Sample

The population in this study were 215 female employees with contract employee status at a automotive company in Tangerang. The questionnaires were distributed using simple random sampling techniques. The results of the questionnaire returned and valid were 170 samples (79.07 percent of the population).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sample Description

Table 2. Sample Descriptive Information

Criteria		amount	%
Age (as of October 2019)	<30 years	21	15.1%
	30 - 40 years	106	76.3%
	> 40 years	12	8.6%
The period of service as a contract employee	<5 years	100	71.9%
	5-10 years	34	24.5%
	> 10 years	5	3.6%
Highest diploma	S1	105	75.5%
	= High school	34	24.5%

Test Results of the Validity and Reliability of Research Indicators

The measurement model testing stage includes testing for convergent validity, discriminant validity. Meanwhile, to test the construct reliability, Cronbach's alpha and

composite reliability were used. The results of the PLS analysis can be used to test the research hypothesis if all indicators in the PLS model have met the requirements of convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability testing.

Discriminant Validity Testing

Discriminant validity is done to ensure that each concept of each latent variable is different from other latent variables. The model has good discriminant validity if the AVE squared value of each exogenous construct (the value on the diagonal) exceeds the correlation between that construct and other constructs (values below the diagonal) (Ghazali, 2014). The results of discriminant validity testing using the AVE square value, namely by looking at the Fornell-Larcker Criterion Value obtained as referred to in Table 4. The results of the discriminant validity test in table 4 above indicate that all constructs have a square root value of AVE above the correlation value with the construct. other latency, through the Fornell-Larcker criteria, so it can be concluded that the model has met the discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Constructing Reliability Testing

The construct reliability can be assessed from the Cronbach's alpha value and the composite reliability of each construct. The recommended composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values are more than 0.7 (Ghazali, 2014), can use the size of one of them. If the composite reliability value is above 0.7, then it is sufficient (Ghozali, 2014). The reliability test results in table 3 above show that all constructs have a composite reliability value greater than 0.7 (> 0.7). In conclusion, all constructions have met the required reliability.

Discussion

Work-Family Conflict Relationship and Job Satisfaction

The results of data analysis in Table 6 show that work-family conflict has no significant effect on job satisfaction. Evidenced by the t-statistics value of 0.879 is smaller than 1.96 and the p-value of 0.380 is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the conclusion is that the H1 hypothesis is rejected. So, it can be concluded that there is no significant effect of work-family conflict on job satisfaction. This finding is different from the conclusion of the research (Hsu, 2011) who mentioned that *work-family conflict* negative effect on job satisfaction. Similar conclusions were also conveyed by (Armstrong et al., 2015). Phenomenon *work-family conflict* yang not It influences job satisfaction and does not have a negative effect, it is very likely that it is driven by other factors, such as urgent financial needs, so that any conflicts that occur at home or outside of work have no effect on job satisfaction. It can also be influenced by internal motivation, such as religious work behavior, which is inherent in the perceptions of female employees, that they are working solely in order to please God Almighty, not merely pursuing material pursuits. The conclusion of this study is the same as the conclusion of the study (Supardi et al., 2020).

Relationship between Work-Family Conflict and Organizational Commitment

The results of data analysis in Table 6 show that the WFC has a significant effect on organizational commitment, which includes all three dimensions, namely *affective commitment*, *continuance commitment*, and *normative commitment*. Evidenced by the t-statistical value listed in Table 6 is greater than 1.96 and the p-value is smaller than 0.05, and all beta coefficients are positive, namely WFC \rightarrow AC

(0.596), WFC → CC (0.521), and WFC → NC (0.540). In conclusion, the hypotheses H2, H3 and H4 are rejected. These findings differ from the conclusions empirical and theoretical findings from previous research from (Zain & Setiawati, 2019) who found evidence that there is no significant relationship between WFC and organizational commitment among medical employees in one of the hospitals studied. The findings of this study explain that WGC experienced by female employees in the automotive industry does not have a negative effect on organizational commitment, but even in this study concludes that there is a positive and significant correlation between WFC and organizational commitment. This bias is possible because of the strong internal motivation of female employees of the automotive industry, and this needs to be investigated further and in-depth. Research (Santoso et al., 2020) mentions that one of the intrinsic motivation in question is the motivation to hope for Dadi Wong (wanting to be a successful person).

Organizational Commitment Relationship and Job Satisfaction

The results of data analysis in Table 6 show that continuance commitment and normative commitment have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. On H6 (CC → JS), as evidenced by the value of t-statistics 3.130 is greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.002 is smaller than 0.05. In conclusion, hypothesis H6 is accepted. Whereas on H7 (NS → JS), It is proven by the t-statistics value of 2.409 which is greater than 1.96 and the p-value of 0.016 is smaller than 0.05. In conclusion, hypothesis H7 is accepted. The conclusion of this study is in accordance with the results of the research (Hedayat et al., 2018). Meanwhile, affective commitment has no effect on job satisfaction. This is evidenced by the t-statistics that the value of 1.873 is smaller than 1.96 and the p-value of 0.062 is greater than 0.05. In conclusion, hypothesis H5 is rejected.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

From the data analysis that has been done, it has been proven that the independent variables *work-family conflict* (WFC) has no significant effect on job satisfaction, but WFC has a significant effect on all dimension's *organizational commitment*, namely affective, continuance, and normative. This study also concluded that *organizational commitment (continuance and normative)* serves as a mediator for the relationship between the WFC and job satisfaction. Meanwhile, affective commitment does not function as a mediator for the relationship between WFC and job satisfaction among female employees in the automotive industry in Tangerang.

Suggestion

It is advisable for future studies to conduct research in other sectors apart from automotive, such as the service industry, finance, education and other sectors so as to enrich this research topic. In addition, it is advisable to increase the number of populations and samples so as to produce a more comprehensive research conclusion. Likewise, in future studies, it would be better to add and include other relevant variables, such as motivation, leadership, HR practice and so on so that it will make research on this theme more complete.

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